

CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY PRACTICES AMONG DOT ACCREDITED HOTEL ESTABLISHMENTS IN CALABARZON REGION

**Noelah Mae D. Borbon
Lyceum of the Philippines University Batangas**

Abstract: This study aimed to assess the CSR practices of the DOT Accredited hotel establishments in CALABARZON region. More specifically, the study sought answer to the following objectives: identify the practices of the accommodation establishment in terms of environmental effort, philanthropical effort, social engagement, and ethical labour practices. Furthermore, the study proposed a framework of CSR focusing on the significance and practices of the hotel establishments. With total of one hundred thirty (130) respondents from the forty-five (45) hotel establishment the result shows that the hotel, resorts, and tourist inn have higher level of corporate social responsibility practices primarily in the environment related efforts. Also, results show that hotel established often practiced CSR in relation to environment effort and thus the researcher recommends for Hotel Management to give focus to the issue on climate change and issue on pollution by coming up with an awareness program to their benefactors that would result to environmental protection. As an output, a framework was proposed for the hotel establishment continuous improvement and innovations.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility; Hotel; Innovations; Practices

Background of the Study

Commitment is the attitude to work really hard to achieve a certain goal. Being committed for continuous improvement would demand full effort, allotting time and even may require sacrifice. Given the fact that commitment is crucial to any business, Corporate Social Responsibility is also essential because it is the heart and soul and is an important standard of modern corporations. It is an indispensable mechanism for both increased corporate accountability, profitability, and environmental sustainability. Moreover, 2017 is commemorated as the year of Corporate Social Responsibility (Cone Communications CSR Study, 2017). However, there are emerging issues and challenges on low commitment of the hospitality industry, more specifically the hotels and resorts, when it comes to CSR hence, these issues are the major problems that this study would like to address. In the Philippine law, CSR is being mandated. In compliance to Section 3 of House bill 306 commonly known as Corporate Code of the Philippines, wherein all the business establishments are encouraged and required to implement, participate and support any CSR initiative in the operation of the business may it be in public or private organization. Over a thousand of books and journals, there are no specific given meaning of CSR, thus Corporate Social Responsibility defines depending on the core value and mission of each business. According to study, the development of corporate social responsibility consciousness is an outcome of the changing of the consumers' ways of thinking (Chai, Chang, Wang & Bre, 2015). The practices may pertain to the environmental effort of a business, philanthropical practices, social engagement, and ethical labour practices. Over the previous decades, CSR has been an essential part of the innovative research for most of the academe and industry practitioners (Aguinis & Glavas, 2012). This study is made to assess the consciousness and awareness in the CSR of hotel establishments. Being the fast-growing hospitality industry, they must also be the first one to have the passion and a heart in helping and reaching out for the community and to the environment making it as part of their commitment. For the hotel industry, measuring the effort they put on promoting tourism shall be equal to their effort in giving back to the community. With this study, the researcher would

like to assess the CSR of hotel and resorts and to propose an action plan for continuous improvement in CALABARZON region. Thus, demonstrating a strong commitment from the top management creates power to lead the people in developing the sense of social responsibility for the community.

Method

The respondents of the study are the employees of the Department of Tourism (DOT) accredited hotel industry. The researcher emailed the DOT regional director to have the updated list of accredited hotels, resorts, and tourist inns in CALABARZON region. Appendix C contains the updated list of the respondents. Out of seventy-six (76) DOT Accredited which is composed of hotel, resort, tourist inn and hotel-resort, 45 or 59.2% participated in the study. There are three four-star hotels, eight (8) three-star hotels, ten two-star hotels, five one-star hotels, thirteen hotel-resorts, eleven tourist Inns and twenty-six (26) resorts. Selected employees who are working in the establishment answered the questionnaire and the managers and supervisors are interviewed while those employees who answered the questionnaires participated the focus group discussion. Upon the data gathering, a total of one hundred thirty (130) respondents from the forty-five (45) hotel establishment served as the actual respondents. Personal encoding was successfully done by the researcher after gathering all the data. SPSS was used to interpret and analyse the data gathered. This study used frequency distribution, percentage and weighted mean as statistical tools for the first part of the questionnaire, presenting the profile of the respondents and the use of the weighted mean was applicable in determining the hotel establishment's corporate social responsibility practices ANOVA was used to test the difference in the perceived actual practices when the respondents are grouped according to the classification of establishment, number of years in operation and location. In accordance with the Code of Ethics, the researcher ensured that all the data to be collected from the respondents will be free consent- fully volunteered from the respondents. The researcher also ensured that there is a high reverence and value regarding the integrity of their respondents in the treatment to receive an effective response from them. Hence, respecting the ideas and opinions of the respondents and recoding their advice on the research topic can ensure a fruitful study.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: CSR Practices in Terms of Environmental Effort

Indicators	WM	VI	R
1. Comply with or surpass set environmental laws, rules, and regulations to promote environmental protection and minimize	3.63	A	1
2. Hotel product is environmentally friendly, creating energy efficient product	3.42	O	6
3. Ensuring environmental sustainability, ecological balance, protection of flora and fauna, animal welfare, agroforestry, conservation of natural resources and maintaining quality of soil, air, and water	3.43	O	5
4. The Hotel is one in conserving energy and water resources	3.45	O	4
5. The Hotel promote in the recycling efforts	3.45	O	3
6. The Hotel uses natural plants as interior design.	3.49	O	2
Composite Mean	3.48	O	

Scale: 3.50-4.00: Always (practiced daily); 2.50-3.49: Often (practiced quarterly); 1.50-2.49: Sometimes (practiced annually); 1.00-1.49: Never (never practiced)

Table 1 presents the CSR practices in terms of Environmental Effort. The computed composite mean score of 3.48 implies that the employees have positive response on the CSR practice in terms of Environmental aspect. The respondents agree that the hotel complies with the environmental laws and regulation that support in protecting the environment (3.63) and the hotel has natural plants as their interior design (3.49). Moreover, the respondents believe that the hotel practices recycling efforts (3.45) and conserving energy and water resources (3.45). However, the hotel product is environmentally friendly (3.42) obtained the least weighted mean score. Complying with the environmental laws to promote environmental protection ranks first in CSR practices in terms of environmental aspect. One of the environmental laws is the Republic Act 903 of 2000 commonly known as the Ecological Solid Waste Management. The recent disclosure in Boracay for rehabilitation and giving the island a break for six months is an effect of the improper waste management.

The respondents affirm that the hotel establishment in CALABARZON is complying with the environmental issue, making that in the first rank. This only proves that hotel management manages very well and must continue with the Corporate Social Responsibility goal which leads to environmental protection. Hotels are the most vulnerable industry to climate change because of their fixed assets (Su, et al., 2013). Climate change is one of the global issues that everyone should be aware of. In a fast-growing industry like hotel and resorts, abiding the environmental rules and regulation is very essential as in the recent study, Ettinger, et al., (2018) highlighted that hotel strongly communicated supplier and environmental issues. The community-based efforts are essential to make it possible to create a full sustenance of the idea to a shared disaster planning led by the community (Orchiston, 2013). There should be a collaborative effort among the community and the hotel chains with regards to environment so that the CSR would be successful.

Hotel product is environmentally friendly, creating energy efficient product ranked last in terms of environmental aspect. Hotel main product is the service provided by the employees. These are indispensable and intangible product that is an essential part of the guest over-all experience. Looking into the environmentally friendly product of the hotel, it is important to consider these room amenities that have atmosphere where in the guest would feel like at home and near to nature. However, it is quite challenging on the part of the hotel establishments since it would demand a large amount of investment in creating an environmentally friendly, creating energy efficient product, though the return on investment would be as high since it would save a lot of energy cost and would save Mother Earth as a solution to the emerging concern on global warming. Fewer hotels used pen rather, than recycled paper as part of the complimentary features in the side table. The core of the hotel product is the guest room itself, providing accommodation to the guest. It is essential to consider energy efficient product. CSR in terms of environmental aspects are progressively vital to the hotel industry, which makes Green hotel enter in the business of hospitality industry (Barber, 2014).

Moreover, as United Nation World Tourism Organization, commonly known as the UNWTO has come up with this sustainable development goals, one of the key indicators is relating to the environment where environmental protection, conservation and awareness is now the priority of the international hospitality and tourism industry to resolve the emerging global issues such as global warming and climate change.

Table 2: CSR Practices in Terms of Philanthropical Effort

Indicators	WM	VI	R
1. Hotels give more back to the community that can benefit the local community programs.	3.32	O	1
2. Hotel practice CSR by donating to national and local charity.	3.17	O	4
3. The Hotel assist people in acquiring marketable skills to reduce poverty	3.31	O	2
4. The Hotel has a foundation to assist in learning or education for the public	3.21	O	3
5. Employees attend fundraising events that help non-profit organization	3.10	O	5
Composite Mean	3.22	O	

Table 2 indicates the CSR practices in terms of Philanthropical Aspect. The computed composite mean score of 3.22 implies that the employees have positive response on the environmentally friendly, creating energy efficient product practice of hotel establishments in terms of philanthropical aspect. Giving back to the community is the commonly practiced item as it is in the first rank (3.32). Hotel assures CSR initiatives that would enable the community to have marketable skills which ranked second (3.31). The respondent affirms that the hotel supports the education through a foundation (3.21) and donates to local or national charity (3.17). Hotel employees attend to fundraising events ranked the lowest weighted mean of 3.22. The respondents confirmed that the hotel has local community programs to give back to the community which ranks first in terms of philanthropical aspect. Giving back to community what is due to them is essential for CSR goal.

For any hospitality industry who is in the service industry, it is but important to also serve the community where the hotel is located. Most especially for the resort business, most of the services offered are in respect with nature, thus not only for the community but also giving nurture to the nature is very important. As what Schuyt (2013) expressed, in this modern age, there is an option for hotels to also upgrade and create a modernized philanthropical commitment which involves funding to local community, volunteering to a charitable program or in a church service. This is a hotel Corporate Social Responsibility towards philanthropy after years of separation from wellbeing nation debating between the role and responsibilities of government and the market, a renewed focus on philanthropy has shown that many societies also harbor a growing voluntary hospitality sector.

On the other hand, employees attend fundraising events that help non-profit organization obtained the least weighted mean score of 3.10. One hotel shares their CSR activity, which was started last 2016, the employees of Batangas Country Club are the one who organize the annual concert for a Cause. This concert is a fundraising effort of the hotel employees to raise fund to be able to build up the community. They invited artist and bands, recently they were able to raise fund to build a hall for the church nearby. The hotel employees were inspired to make it an annual event of the hotel. This CSR initiatives are really towards working hand in hand to support community aspirations and seeing them through reality is the essence of a meaningful public service. Aside from assisting the community' needs, this simple CSR also provides self-fulfilment and boost the confidence and re affirming of the hotel employees that it feels, and it is good to be of help and be used as an instrument to make other people's life better and making a difference with a simple act of random kindness, that is Corporate Social Responsibility.

Table 3: CSR Practices in Terms of Social Engagement

Indicators	WM	VI	R
1. Hotel has a project to improve the management and access of water used by a farming community, to foster public health	3.14	O	2
2. The Hotel inform local communities of mining plans and programs through continuous dialogue to promote awareness of safety and environmental policies.	2.94	O	5
3. The Hotel has a program volunteering in community service and charity.	3.08	O	4
4. The Hotel supports in giving resources for the victims of calamity within the area.	3.20	O	1
5. Employee volunteerism hits inside the home as well by participating in various food programs	3.12	O	3
Composite Mean	3.10	O	

Scale: 3.50-4.00: Always (practiced daily); 2.50-3.49: Often (practiced quarterly); 1.50-2.49: Sometimes (practiced annually); 1.00-1.49: Never (never practiced)

Table 3 indicates the CSR practices in terms of social aspect. The computed composite mean score of 3.10 implies that the employees have positive response on the CSR practice in terms of social aspect. The respondents affirm that the hotel provides generously for the victims of calamity (3.20). Part of the project of the hotel is the improvement of the management and fostering public health (3.14) as well as the hotel promotes employee volunteerism (3.12). Moreover, the respondents assert that there is program in volunteering in any charity service and charity (3.08) informing the local community got the lowest weighted mean of 2.94.

First in the ranking, the respondents affirm that the hotel provide generously for the victim of calamity (3.20). Philippines, as a developed country would not hide the fact that this country cannot run away from natural disaster. In fact, Philippine is as third most disaster risk country in the world. Numerous typhoons, earthquake, and other natural occurrence cause thousand and millions of damages to human and even infrastructure. As one of the managers in Quezon confirmed the most tragic typhoon that they experienced was Typhoon Glenda last 2014. As reported by Regional Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (RDRRMC), there were 43 casualties, majority of these was from Quezon province. As part of the Corporate Social Responsibility initiative by one of the resorts in Quezon, the management, together with the entire employees helped out in giving out donations for the victims of the tragic typhoon. Furthermore, according to Galindo, et al., (2014) the country is moderately ready and prepared for these natural disasters. However, knowing the kind of infrastructure such as facilities, utilities, and transportation within, the nation is less prepared. For the hotel industry, generous giving to victims is number one priority in their CSR activity. Being the first in rank in Social engagement, it is evident that people working in the hotel industry are good hearted, and people oriented (Prince & Khaleq, 2013). Moreover, according to Johansson et.al, (2014) affirms that in the occurrence of natural disaster, the hotel and resort is generous in donating to the victims nearby their location.

Finally, lowest in the obtained weighted mean is to promote awareness of safety and environmental policies by having a dialogue to inform the local communities of mining plans

and programs (2.94). This issue in mining, safety and environmental policies is being prioritized by the Department of Environment and Natural Resources. The hotel, specifically those located nearby the mining sites in elevated areas are greatly affected by this issue, the more that they are merely concerned in creating awareness and creating program to lessen the massive problem about the issue. Being this as the lowest in the ranking only shows that the hotel industry should consider informing their local community and address the main concern as part of their CSR goals. According to Ham and Han, (2013) the hospitality industry should consider the environmental impact; likewise, it is essential for the management to inculcate and observe environmental practices as emerging social cause. This could be made possible by inserting the concern of the local community by creating awareness program and rehabilitation.

Table 4: CSR Ethical Labour Practices Effort

Indicators	WM	VI	R
1. Developing an employee bonus program that awards workers who figure out how to make the company's goods even more sustainable.	3.22	O	7
2. Employees are formally trained by the Management.	3.27	O	5
3. The code of ethics is clearly communicated to employees.	3.38	O	1.5
4. The Hotel is more transparent about their business.	3.31	O	4
5. Top Management is treating employees fairly.	3.25	O	6
6. The Management treat employees well, give equal opportunities and better pay.	3.35	O	3
7. Hotel employees are paid for time off if they are volunteering	3.18	O	8
8. As part of the CSR, the Hotel Management promotes gender equality, empowering women	3.38	O	1.5
Composite Mean	3.29	O	

Scale: 3.50-4.00: Always (practiced daily); 2.50-3.49: Often (practiced quarterly); 1.50-2.49: Sometimes (practiced annually); 1.00-1.49: Never (never practiced)

Table 4 indicates the CSR practices in terms of ethical labour practices the computed composite mean score of 3.10 implies that the employees have positive response on the CSR practice in terms of ethical labour practices. First in the rank, the employees react positively that the code of ethics is clearly disseminated to them and gender equality is also promoted as well as empowering women (3.38). The hotel affirms that they treat the employees by giving fair opportunity and good paying salary (3.35). The respondents affirm that the hotel is transparent with business (3.31) and the management trains their employees (3.27). Moreover, top management is treating employees fairly (3.25) and the hotel has an employee bonus program that awards workers who actively participate in achieving CSR goals got the lowest obtained weighted mean of 3.22.

First in the rank, the employees react positively that the code of ethics is clearly disseminated to them (3.38). Dissemination of code of ethics is one of the responsibilities of the human resources. Generally, the code of ethics is discussed during the hiring process, if not in a separate operational meeting. However, in some cases like small scale hotels, they made use of paper dissemination and indicating that to their employee's manual and letting the employee sign agreeing that they have read and fully understand what is written in the manual. According to Lee and Tsang (2013), there is an increasing concern with regards to ethics in the working environment as there is also a growing complexity to the hotel industry. Thus, hotel front liners agreed that ethics is one of the most essential issues that are being faced in today's generation. As the recent study reveals, if a working environment has a positive ethical value,

this will equate to a healthy working environment which may result to job satisfaction thus enhanced customer satisfaction and eventually increasing the profit (Knani, 2014). As it is clearly seen, being the first in the rank only proved that dissemination of code of ethics as part of the CSR is a good advantage on the part of the hotel in return.

Gender equality is also promoted as well as empowering women (3.38) also topped in the ranking. One HR manager affirms that they have no gender requirement in hiring for a position, both men and women are now doing the same job as prescribed in the job description; however, they have included minimum age as a requirement. Also, in a developing country like the Philippines, gender equality is no longer an issue. Everyone, regardless of the gender is given equal opportunity. As it is also evidently seen during the data gathering process, most of the front office staff that the researcher talked to are in equal number for men and women. In Addition to that, in the recent report in Global Gender Gap of 2014 by World Economic Forum, out of 142 countries, Philippines is in the 9th rank in terms of Gender Equality (MacPhail, 2015). Furthermore, according to Bayeh (2016), when women are being empowered in all means and when gender equality is being achieved, it is the only time when the country will achieve sustainable development. This calls for the commitment of concerned people to be conscious of giving equal opportunity. Effective gender equality will result to positively perceived CSR initiatives that in return has a big impact on customer loyalty (Kim and Kim, 2016).

However, the lowest in the obtained weighted mean of 3.22, is developing an employee bonus program that awards workers who figure out how to make the company’s goods even more sustainable. Having this bonus reward system boost the morale of the employees as it encourages and motivates people to be more active in participating. However, originally, CSR is a volunteer act. Awards system is just an additional self-fulfillment that the employee may receive. Nonetheless, additional awards and cash incentive may be added for boosting factor and motivation for others to also participate but is not necessary. Making it the lowest rank proves that the hotel, resort and tourist’s inn may lack bonus program such as giving awards and recognition. According to Zientara, et al., (2015) a hotel company who wanted an end goal of committed and well-engaged employees should consider and embrace CSR. In the recent study of Radwan (2015), he found that to enhance the organizational commitment, CSR should be considered, However, CSR is not being considered for employee retention. Given the data that these received the lowest rank, hospitality establishments must include CSR edges with regards to maintainable approach to develop their worker. Business standards is being refined amongst personnel by participating the hotel CSR initiatives and engaging in any activity related to the corporate social responsibility where their social skills are being observed (Luu, 2017).

Table 5: Summary of CSR Practices

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Ethical Labour Practices	3.29	Often	2
1. Social Engagement	3.10	Often	4
2. Philanthropic Effort	3.22	Often	3
3. Environmental Effort	3.48	Often	1
Composite Mean	3.27	Often	

Table 5 presents the summary of the CSR practices of hotel industry. The computed composite mean score of 3.22 implies that the employees have positive response on the CSR practices. The most commonly practiced CSR among hotel establishments is in relation to environment (3.48) followed by practices relating to ethical labour (3.29) and philanthropic (3.22). The

least practiced in corporate social responsibility in the social engagement having the weighted mean of 3.10.

Environmental effort is the most practiced CSR among hotel establishments gearing towards sustainable tourism. The world tourism organization promotes environmental protection through the platform 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) where it focuses on 17 key areas that the hotel, resorts and other tourism business should be prioritizing which is in line to the global agenda for people, planet, prosperity and peace. Moreover, those corporate social responsibility practices of hotel industry relating to ethical and philanthropical followed as it also depicts higher responsibility among the hotel management to be considerate of and be committed to attain their CSR goals. However, the least practiced corporate social responsibility is in relation to social engagement nonetheless the hotel knows there is a need to improve on this matter. In addition to that, as Gao and Mattila (2014) perceived, the friendliness and capability of the hotel employees may intervene with the service results and guest's delight. The hotel employees are more effective when they were motivated thus in return customer will be satisfied. Since based on the research findings of Liu, et al, (2017) who suggested to hospitality industry to observe their employee's engagement to CSR to create awareness and self-fulfilment to organizational sustainable projects. This may result to an improved hotel performance and profitability.

Figure 1. Proposed CSR Framework

The framework is composed of Corporate Social Responsibility practices on the right side It is arranged based on the degree of importance and weight. For CSR practices, the commonly practiced CSR among hotel industry are those of environmental effort (3.48) followed by ethical labour practices (3.29) and then philanthropical effort (3.22) and social engagement as the least practiced (3.10). On the other hand, the Significance of CSR is at the left side, also arranged based on its weight. CSR evolves within the four main and core responsibilities. Economic depicts the corporation's ability to be profitable, legal, which mainly concern with obeying the law; ethical is tackling about knowing what is right and fair and philanthropical depicts being a good corporate citizen (Carroll,1983; Dudovskiy, 2012).

Hotel CSR Practices are associated with the significance of corporate social responsibility which are considered the core of this framework that possibly determines the commitment of the hotel industry towards a positive implementation of corporate social responsibility. Moreover, this framework made use of pyramid, as inspired by Carroll's Pyramid. In ancient time, pyramid in Egypt are used as a tomb for those of the highest form of humankind such as king, pharaoh, gods and goddesses. Its foundation is as strong as a rock building for thousands of years. In relation to CSR, let CSR be the foundation of hotel industry which shall be strong as rock, making that as everyone's commitment to strive continuously thus, its goals will be only achieved in years' time with commitment as the foundation.

Moreover, according to Posadas (2017), colour also gives meaning and emphasis to what it depicts. Economic aspect is in dark green which means monetary success representing corporations' capability to be profitable. Philanthropic aspect is in blue which means betterment of humanity signifying the ability to improve one's quality of life. Legal aspect is in orange which means justice and legal matters that demonstrate obeying the law. Ethical aspect is in violet which means influence and spiritual power that separate what is right and fair to do from what is immoral. Furthermore, those in light green are the hotel's CSR practices which means mother earth and hope.

Proposed CSR Framework

Hotel environment and social practices influence economic aspect in such a manner that corporate social responsibility practices to minimize the expenditures of the company while increasing the profit by cultivating the image of the company and up building the customer loyalty. Hotel in today's generation are now gearing towards green hotel where in hotels all over the world are more conscious in protecting the environment as well as the social being. It is the commitment of the hotels to go green by ensuring environment and social practices which in return will improve the economic stability of the business establishment. Reduce, Reuse and Recycle are most commonly practiced by the hotels to promote efficient waste management, In addition, numerous hotels recycle used paper as an inter-department communication not only for cost cutting but also to save more. Legal aspect denotes that the hotel has the commitment to abide the law, boosting the engagement of the employees and increasing the public image and the hotel's reputation. This only proves that the environment and social CSR practices influence the legal aspect of the hotel. One of these practices is the hotel's commitment for continuous dialogue with the local community regarding the safety and environmental policies. Aside from the enumerated CSR practices, hotels are also encouraged and has the commitment to train and treat their employees making it as their social responsibility to obey the labor law. According to the UNWTO Secretary-General Zurab Pololikashvili (2018), innovation and tourism investment are not ends in themselves; they are means to develop better tourism products, to improve the governance of tourism and to make the most of the proven sustainability of tourism, by creating jobs and generating opportunities.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Hotel establishments around CALABARZON are mostly located around coastal areas of Batangas; they exist between 6-10 years, providing accommodation and luxury to tourists away from home. The hotel, resorts and tourist inn have higher level of corporate social responsibility practices primarily in the environment related efforts. Moreover, Resorts have significantly

higher view on the level of significance of CSR in terms of legal aspect as well as on the CSR practices compared to tourist inn; meanwhile, those respondents from accommodations with 6-10 years in operations of CSR in terms of economic aspect have at the same time with lower problems encountered in terms of social aspect. CSR officer may be elected as part of the public relation or human resource to monitor the CSR activities and its effect to the economic stability of the hotel, resorts, and tourists' inn. Points and reward program may be utilized by the hotel, resorts, and tourist inn. This may be awarded to boost volunteerism and be involved in community CSR initiative. Also, as a recommendation, Universities in CALABARZON may strengthen their CSR program and insert CSR as part of their curriculum to widen the CSR commitment. Moreover, the Hotel Management may give focus to the issue on climate change and issue on pollution by coming up with an awareness program to their benefactors that would result to environmental protection

References

- Aguinis, H. and Glavas, A. (2012). 'What We Know and Don't Know about Corporate Social Responsibility: A Review and Research Agenda', *Journal of Management*, 38, 4, 932-968.
- Barber, N. A. (2014). Profiling the potential "green" hotel guest: Who are they and what do they want? *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 38(3), 361-387.
- Chai J, Chang, P., Wang, Z. and Bre, Y. (2015) The Public Perception of Corporate Social Responsibility and Its Effects on Customer Behaviour in China, *American Journal of Industrial and Business Management*, 2015, 5, 611-621.
- Cone Communications CSR Study. (2017) Retrieved on Jan 20, 2018, retrieved from: from www.conecomm.com
- Dudovskiy, J. (2012). Carroll's Corporate Social Responsibility Pyramid and its applications to small and medium sized businesses. Retrieved July 2018, from research-methodology.net
- Ettinger, A., Grabner-Kräuter, S., & Terlutter, R. (2018). Online Corporate Social Responsibility communication in the hotel industry: Evidence from small hotels. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 68, 94-104.
- Galindo, R. P., Villanueva, G. V., & Enguito, M. R. C. (2014). Organizational Preparedness for Natural Disasters in Ozamiz City, Philippines. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 3(1).
- Gao, Y. L., & Mattila, A. S. (2014). Improving consumer satisfaction in green hotels: The roles of perceived warmth, perceived competence, and CSR motive. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 42.
- Ham, S., & Han, H. (2013). Role of perceived fit with hotels' green practices in the formation of customer loyalty: Impact of environmental concerns. *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research*, 18(7), 731-748.
- Kim, S. B., & Kim, D. Y. (2016). The influence of corporate social responsibility, ability, reputation, and transparency on hotel customer loyalty in the US: a gender-based approach. *Springer Plus*, 5(1), 1537.
- Knani, M. (2014). Ethics in the hospitality industry: Review and research agenda. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 9(3), 1.
- Lee, L. Y. S., & Tsang, N. K. (2013). Perceptions of tourism and hotel management students on ethics in the workplace. *Journal of teaching in travel & tourism*, 13(3), 228-250.
- Liu, F., Wang, X., Tian, X., & Tang, Y. (2017,). The effect of corporate social responsibility on hotel employees' work outcomes: The mediating role of organizational identification. In *Service Systems and Service Management*, International Conference on (1-5). IEEE.
- Luu, T.T. (2017). CSR and organizational citizenship behaviour for the environment in hotel industry: The moderating roles of corporate entrepreneurship and employee attachment style. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 29(11).
- MacPhail, F. (2015). Is gender inequality really so low in the Philippines? Retrieved June 11, 2018, from <http://www.eastasiaforum.org>

- Orchiston, C. (2013). Tourism business preparedness, resilience and disaster planning in a region of high seismic risk: The case of the Southern Alps, New Zealand. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 16(5), 477–494. Retrieved from: www.mendeley.com
- Posadas, S. (2017). The Meaning of Colours. Retrieved June 2018, from <http://sibagraphics.com>
- Prince, P. R., & Khaleq, Z. B. (2013). Assessment of Gap Between Service Quality Expectation and Perception: A Study on the Walk-In Guests of Economic Hotels in Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh. *IUP Journal of Marketing Management*, 12(3), 7.
- Radwan, H. R. I. (2015). The Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility on Employees in the Hotel Sector. *International Journal of Tourism & Hospitality Reviews*, 2(1), 85-96.
- 2014 Survey of Tourism Establishments in the Philippines (STEP) - Economy Wide: Preliminary Results. (2016). retrieved from: psa.gov.ph.
- Schuyt, T. N. M. (2013). Philanthropy and the philanthropy sector: An introduction. *Philanthropy and the Philanthropy Sector: An Introduction* (pp. 1–158). Ashgate Publishing Ltd. Retrieved from <http://www.scopus.com/>
- Su, Y. P., Hall, C. M., & Ozanne, L. (2013). Hospitality industry responses to climate change: A benchmark study of Taiwanese tourist hotels. *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research*, 18(1-2), 92-107.
- Zientara, P., Kujawski, L., & Bohdanowicz-Godfrey, P. (2015). Corporate social responsibility and employee attitudes: evidence from a study of Polish hotel employees. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 23(6), 859-880.

Contributor: *Dr Noelah Mae D. Borbon, IHM, CGSP, CITHM & Graduate School, Lyceum of the Philippines University, Capitol Site, Batangas City.*

Corresponding Author: *Dr Noelah Mae D. Borbon. Email: nmdborbon@lpubatangas.edu.ph*